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Privacy-Preserving AI on Edge Devices: A Comparative Study of On-Device Learning and Cloud Processing

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ABSTRACT

The rise of edge computing has transformed how artificial intelligence (AI) processes personal and sensitive data. Traditional cloud-based AI architectures raise privacy concerns due to the transmission and centralized storage of user data. On-device learning, by contrast, enables local inference, enhancing data privacy and reducing network dependency. This study conducts a comparative analysis of on-device learning and cloud-based AI processing using a human activity recognition (HAR) task. We evaluate both approaches on model accuracy, latency, energy consumption, and privacy exposure. Our findings reveal that while cloud-based models slightly outperform in accuracy and energy efficiency, on-device models offer significantly lower latency and enhanced privacy by eliminating the need for data transmission. The results support a privacy-preserving edge AI paradigm, particularly for applications in healthcare, personal security, and mobile computing. Recommendations are provided to guide system architects in selecting deployment strategies aligned with privacy, performance, and regulatory requirements.

Keywords:-Edge AI, On-Device Learning, Cloud Processing, Privacy-Preserving AI, Human Activity Recognition, Federated Learning, IoT Security, Latency Optimization, Differential Privacy, Energy Efficiency

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has rapidly become embedded in everyday devices, from smartphones and wearables to Internet of Things (IoT) sensors. This integration supports an expanding range of applications, including mobile health diagnostics, smart surveillance, and autonomous systems. As user expectations for real-time responsiveness and personalized services increase, AI has emerged as a core enabler of modern edge computing. Traditionally, such AI systems have relied heavily on cloud-based processing, where data is transmitted to remote servers for training and inference. While cloud computing offers substantial computational resources, it introduces significant privacy, security, and compliance concerns, particularly in sensitive sectors such as healthcare, finance, and personal security.

Cloud-based AI workflows inherently require the transfer of sensitive data beyond the local device; even when data in transit is encrypted, the centralized nature of cloud platforms creates high-value targets for cyberattacks and insider threats. Misconfigurations, insufficient access controls, and the opaque handling of user data further exacerbate these risks (Luqman et al., 2024; Chauhan et al., 2023). The scale of potential breaches in centralized architectures is amplified by the aggregation of vast datasets, making them especially vulnerable despite encryption safeguards. Additionally, cloud architectures often conflict with the principles of data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which mandate data minimization, user control, and algorithmic transparency (Shastri et al., 2019).

Centralized systems may retain excessive data, restrict users' ability to manage or erase personal information, and obscure algorithmic processes, hindering

compliance with privacy-by-design obligations.

The regulatory landscape in Nigeria reflects similar concerns. The Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR, 2019) and the Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA, 2023) impose explicit obligations on data controllers and processors, requiring measures such as consent management, compliance audits, and the registration of data handlers. These measures are designed to enforce data minimization, accountability, and oversight. Further, the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) has mandated that sensitive cloud-hosted data in sectors such as healthcare, finance, and government must be stored within Nigeria's borders to safeguard national data sovereignty and enhance regulatory oversight (Techpoint Africa, 2025).

In response to these challenges, there is growing interest in on-device learning and edge AI, which process data directly on local devices. Edge AI minimizes latency, conserves bandwidth, and strengthens privacy by reducing the need to transmit raw data to centralized servers (Gill et al., 2024). In domains such as healthcare and smart manufacturing, these characteristics are critical for ensuring both operational efficiency and data protection. A related paradigm, Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML), extends this approach to highly resource-constrained devices such as microcontrollers. By embedding intelligence into low-power hardware, TinyML enables continuous AI-driven functionality without relying on constant cloud connectivity (Banbury et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). This facilitates privacy-preserving and context-aware applications in remote or bandwidth-limited environments.

However, the resource constraints inherent to TinyML, which include limited computational power, small memory capacity, and restricted energy budgets, introduce unique security challenges.

These include susceptibility to model extraction, adversarial manipulation, and side-channel attacks, which are more difficult to mitigate than in high-capacity cloud environments (Huckelberry et al., 2024). In contrast, cloud-based AI provides virtually unlimited compute and centralized model management but remains an attractive target for cyberattacks. Unit-42(2023) findings reveal that over 80% of security vulnerabilities in organizations stem from cloud systems, with major vectors including web framework takeovers (22.8%), remote access exploits (20.1%), and IT/networking flaws (17.1%) (Infosecurity Magazine, 2023). Insider threats also pose significant risks in cloud architectures, where privileged access when misused or inadequately monitored, can lead to intentional or accidental breaches.

Emerging security solutions such as confidential computing aim to address some of these risks by using hardware-backed Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs). These secure enclaves protect sensitive workloads not only at rest and in transit but also during computation, isolating them even from cloud administrators (Kocaoğullar et al., 2024; Bertani et al., 2025). While promising, such technologies require careful integration into AI workflows to ensure compatibility, performance, and scalability.

This study presents a comparative analysis of privacy-preserving AI paradigms, specifically on-device TinyML learning versus cloud-based processing, across four critical dimensions: security, performance, scalability, and compliance. The aim is to identify design strategies that strike an optimal balance between protecting user data and meeting practical deployment requirements, thereby guiding both future research and real-world implementation in this rapidly evolving domain.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The increasing integration of AI into edge devices, such as smartphones, wearables, and IoT nodes has intensified the need to reconcile high-performance computation with robust privacy safeguards. Cloud-based AI remains dominant due to its virtually unlimited processing power, scalability, and ease of model deployment. However, this paradigm necessitates transmitting raw or semi-processed user data to centralized servers, creating significant exposure to privacy breaches, insider threats, and regulatory non-compliance. Even with encryption, the centralization of sensitive data amplifies the potential scale and impact of security incidents, especially in domains governed by strict data protection frameworks.

On-device learning, particularly within the TinyML paradigm, offers an alternative by retaining data locally and processing it at the source. This aligns with privacy-by-design principles and mitigates risks associated with data transmission. Nevertheless, edge-based AI faces inherent limitations, including restricted computational resources, energy constraints, and potential compromises in model accuracy. These limitations can be further exacerbated in resource-constrained or latency-sensitive environments.

Although both paradigms have been extensively discussed in conceptual and technical literature, empirical comparative studies that evaluate their trade-offs across key performance indicators, such as privacy exposure, latency, accuracy, and energy consumption, which remain scarce. This lack of systematic evidence inhibits informed design and deployment decisions for privacy-preserving AI in real-world applications. This study addresses this gap by conducting a controlled, task-specific comparison of on-device learning and cloud-based AI processing. Through quantitative analysis, it aims to establish

evidence-based insights that inform the development of secure, efficient, and compliant AI systems in edge computing contexts.

RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research is to conduct a systematic, empirical comparison of on-device (TinyML) learning and cloud-based AI processing within edge computing environments, with a focus on balancing privacy preservation, performance, and energy efficiency in real-world applications.

The specific objectives of this study include:

1. Identify and analyse privacy vulnerabilities associated with cloud-based AI processing.
2. Measure and assess the performance of AI models under both paradigms
3. Analyse privacy preservation, performance, and energy efficiency between both approaches on both paradigms
4. Identify Trade-offs and recommend strategies for secure, efficient AI deployment in edge environments.

RELATED WORK

Edge AI: Edge AI refers to the deployment of artificial intelligence models directly on edge devices, such as smartphones, wearables, sensors, and embedded systems, rather than relying on cloud-based processing. This approach allows for real-time data analysis, reduced latency, lower bandwidth usage, and improved privacy, as data can be processed locally without being sent to external servers. The evolution of Edge AI stems from the limitations of traditional cloud computing in handling the vast data generated by IoT devices. Advances in lightweight AI models (TinyML), model compression techniques, and specialized edge hardware (like NVIDIA Jetson or Apple Neural Engine) have made on-

device AI feasible and efficient (Daruvuri & Patibandla, 2023).

Edge AI has significant applications across sectors. In healthcare, it enables continuous patient monitoring and on-device diagnosis, protecting sensitive data. In smart homes, it powers voice assistants, smart cameras, and energy management systems without exposing user data to the cloud. In autonomous systems, such as self-driving cars and drones, Edge AI ensures ultra-fast decision-making by processing data locally, which is essential for safety and reliability. These applications demonstrate how Edge AI balances performance with privacy and responsiveness in data-driven environments.

Cloud-Based AI: Cloud-Based AI refers to the use of centralized cloud infrastructure to train, deploy, and run artificial intelligence models. This architecture leverages powerful cloud servers capable of handling vast amounts of data and complex computations. Major providers such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Microsoft Azure offer services that include model training, inference, and data storage, often through scalable and flexible APIs. These platforms enable organizations to build sophisticated AI systems without investing in costly hardware, and they support advanced capabilities such as large language models, computer vision, and speech recognition. The cloud also facilitates collaboration across distributed teams and supports rapid model updates and deployment at scale.

One of the main advantages of cloud-based AI is its ability to process and learn from large datasets, benefiting from high-performance GPUs and TPUs in cloud data centers. This centralized model allows for consistent performance, easier maintenance, and integration with data lakes and enterprise systems. It also supports continuous model retraining

using real-time or batch data, enhancing accuracy and adaptability. Additionally, cloud platforms typically provide strong development tools, automated scaling, and access to pre-trained models, reducing the technical burden on developers and accelerating time-to-market for AI applications.

Despite these benefits, cloud-based AI has several critical limitations, particularly related to latency, energy consumption, and privacy. Because cloud models require data transmission over the internet, there is often a delay between input and response, making this model less suitable for latency-sensitive tasks like autonomous navigation or emergency medical alerts. Cloud operations also consume significant energy, both on the client side (for continuous connectivity) and at the data center level. Most notably, privacy concerns arise because sensitive user data, such as health records, personal preferences, or behavioural patterns, must leave the local device for remote processing. This exposes users to risks such as data breaches, unauthorized access, and non-compliance with data protection regulations like the GDPR or HIPAA.

Privacy-Preserving AI: Privacy-Preserving AI is a rapidly evolving field that aims to ensure that artificial intelligence systems can operate effectively without compromising the privacy and confidentiality of user data. As AI becomes more embedded in domains like healthcare, finance, and personal communications, it often requires access to sensitive information. The core objective of privacy-preserving AI is to minimize the exposure of raw data while still enabling meaningful insights and accurate model predictions. This means protecting data not just during storage but throughout the entire AI pipeline, from data collection and pre-processing to model training and inference. Privacy-preserving AI supports

ethical data practices and helps organizations comply with regulations like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA, 2023) in Nigeria, California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), and HIPAA in the U.S.

One of the most prominent approaches in this field is Federated Learning (FL). Rather than centralizing data in the cloud, FL enables training of AI models directly on user devices (like smartphones or IoT sensors), keeping data local and secure. Each device computes model updates based on local data, and only these updates (e.g., gradients or model weights) are sent to a central server for aggregation. This decentralized approach significantly reduces the risk of data leakage or unauthorized access. FL is particularly useful in settings like predictive text on mobile phones or personalized healthcare systems, where privacy is critical but data must still contribute to a shared model (Bonawitz, 2019). However, FL can face challenges such as device heterogeneity, communication efficiency, and vulnerability to adversarial attacks like model inversion.

Complementing federated learning is *Differential Privacy (DP)*, a mathematical framework that ensures that the output of a computation does not reveal too much about any individual data point in the dataset. By adding carefully calibrated random noise to queries or model parameters, DP guarantees that the inclusion or exclusion of a single record does not significantly affect the overall output. This makes it extremely difficult for attackers to infer private information from aggregate results. Differential privacy can be applied during data collection, model training, or result sharing. Major tech companies like Apple and Google have implemented DP in their analytics and telemetry systems, demonstrating its practical viability. However, DP introduces a trade-off

between privacy and accuracy, as adding noise may reduce model performance if not properly tuned.

Another promising technique is **Homomorphic Encryption (HE)**, which enables computations to be carried out directly on encrypted data without needing to decrypt it first. This allows sensitive information to remain confidential, even during processing by potentially untrusted third parties like cloud providers. For example, a hospital could encrypt patient data and send it to a cloud AI system that performs predictive analytics without ever accessing the raw data. The results, also encrypted, can be decrypted only by the hospital. Although HE provides strong cryptographic guarantees, it is computationally intensive and often slower than other methods, making it more suitable for specific use cases that can tolerate latency or where data confidentiality is paramount.

Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC) offers another method to preserve privacy during collaborative AI processes. In SMPC, multiple parties jointly compute a function over their inputs while keeping those inputs private from one another. For instance, two hospitals could collaborate to train a machine learning model on their combined datasets without sharing any actual patient records. SMPC achieves this by dividing data into secret shares and distributing them among participants. Computations are performed on these shares, and the final result is obtained without revealing individual contributions. While SMPC is highly secure, it can involve significant communication overhead and complex protocol design, limiting its current scalability to large, distributed AI systems.

Together, these techniques: *Federated Learning, Differential Privacy, Homomorphic Encryption, and Secure Multi-Party Computation* represent the *foundational toolkit of privacy-preserving AI*. Each addresses different points in the

data lifecycle and offers unique trade-offs between privacy, accuracy, computational efficiency, and scalability. In many practical applications, a combination of methods is employed to maximize protection while retaining model utility. *For example, Federated Learning may be combined with Differential Privacy to ensure both decentralized training and formal privacy guarantees.* As AI continues to grow and integrate more deeply into society, privacy-preserving technologies will be essential in building trustworthy, ethical, and secure AI systems.

Recent studies have examined privacy-preserving techniques

The growing body of research comparing edge-based and cloud-based AI architectures reflects the tension between performance, scalability, and privacy in AI system design. Studies such as have shown that while cloud-based AI provides high computational capabilities and model accuracy, it often introduces latency, bandwidth overhead, and data privacy concerns.

On the other hand, edge AI systems reduce response time and enhance privacy by processing data locally, but face constraints in storage, compute power, and model complexity. Comparative evaluations, such as those by Zhang et al. (2021), demonstrate that hybrid models where inference is done on edge and training in the cloud, can balance these trade-offs, although at the cost of increased system complexity.

Other comparative studies, including those by have explored task-specific performance of edge versus cloud AI in domains like smart healthcare, autonomous vehicles, and surveillance. These studies generally agree that for real-time and privacy-sensitive applications, edge AI is preferable, while cloud-based AI remains suitable for large-scale data analytics and centralized model updates.

However, many of these studies lack a consistent benchmarking framework, making it difficult to generalize findings across different hardware, networks, and AI tasks. This suggests a need for standardized performance metrics and unified testbeds to better compare deployment strategies across various contexts.

In parallel, recent research has focused on privacy-preserving methods for AI deployment, motivated by regulatory pressures and ethical concerns. Federated Learning has gained particular attention, with works, outlining its architecture, scalability challenges, and security vulnerabilities. Similarly, advancements in Differential Privacy have been documented in the work of Abadi et al. (2016) and its adoption in Google's and Apple's production systems. These studies reveal that while DP offers theoretical guarantees of privacy, it often comes at the cost of reduced model accuracy, especially in small datasets or complex tasks. Other privacy techniques, including Homomorphic Encryption and Secure Multi-Party Computation, have been evaluated in scenarios such as privacy-preserving medical diagnostics and cross-organizational learning.

Despite progress, current approaches face several limitations. For instance, Federated Learning systems are often vulnerable to data poisoning and model inversion attacks, as highlighted by Bagdasaryan et al. (2020). Additionally, heterogeneity in client devices, communication latency, and inconsistent data availability hinder the scalability and performance of decentralized models. In the case of Differential Privacy, selecting appropriate noise levels remains a challenge, especially when model interpretability and accuracy are critical. Homomorphic Encryption and SMPC, while offering strong cryptographic guarantees, are computationally expensive and often impractical for real-time inference.

Another persistent limitation lies in the trade-off between privacy and utility. Many privacy-preserving techniques degrade model performance or increase system overhead. For example, applying Differential Privacy may significantly reduce prediction accuracy, especially for deep learning models with many parameters. Similarly, SMPC protocols introduce communication bottlenecks when scaling across multiple parties. Furthermore, most current approaches focus on model training, leaving privacy risks during inference and data collection phases less explored. These gaps limit the practical deployment of privacy-preserving AI in edge and cloud environments alike.

Hence, the literature reflects a growing consensus on the need to integrate privacy-preserving techniques into AI deployment strategies. Although, while edge computing offers inherent privacy advantages, it must be complemented by formal privacy methods to achieve robust protection. In the same manner, cloud-based systems require enhanced encryption and distributed learning techniques to reduce exposure risks.

(i.) Abadi et al. (2016) introduced a practical mechanism for training deep learning models with differential privacy by proposing the Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD) algorithm, which enables the protection of training data during the model learning process.

(ii.) Xu et al. (2021) surveyed the architectural challenges, threats, and defenses associated with Edge AI environments, highlighting critical privacy vulnerabilities in both centralized and decentralized systems. However, relatively few studies provide a direct, empirical comparison between on-device inference and cloud-based AI, particularly under realistic deployment constraints such as limited hardware capacity, energy

- consumption, and the need for real-time responsiveness.
- (iii.) Geyer et al. (2017) introduced a client-level differential privacy approach to federated learning, showing that aggregating model updates rather than raw data can effectively mitigate privacy leakage. Their experiments demonstrate that client-level differential privacy can be maintained with minimal impact on model performance, particularly when the number of participating clients is sufficiently large. Nevertheless, they acknowledge persistent challenges, including increased communication overhead and scalability issues, especially under resource-constrained and real-time deployment scenarios.
- (iv.) Deng et al. (2020) examine the convergence of edge computing and artificial intelligence, coining the concept of “edge intelligence.” Their review outlines architectural frameworks that shift AI processing closer to the data source to improve latency and privacy. The study highlights the practical trade-offs between edge and cloud architectures, showing that while the cloud offers higher computational power, edge devices reduce data exposure by minimizing transmission. Although the paper is more conceptual, it references real-world systems and emphasizes the feasibility of deploying lightweight AI models on edge devices to support privacy-sensitive applications.
- (v.) Tian et al. (2019) propose a Lightweight Efficient Parallel Convolutional Neural Network (LEP-CNN) model; a lightweight edge-assisted CNN inference solution for IoT devices. Using an online/offline encryption scheme, their system offloads over 99% of CNN operations to nearby edge servers, yielding up to 35 times inference speedup with AlexNet, all while preserving accuracy. LEP-CNN demonstrates superior efficiency compared to traditional homomorphic encryption-based methods under time-sensitive deployment conditions.
- (vi.) Li et al. (2020) analyses the growing field of federated learning (FL), emphasizing its role in training AI models across distributed edge devices without sharing raw data. Through empirical case studies in healthcare and mobile applications, they show that FL achieves performance close to centralized training while significantly reducing privacy risks. The study highlights challenges such as Non-Independent and Identically Distributed data (non-IID data) and communication overhead but supports FL as a scalable and privacy-conscious solution. Their findings underscore FL’s effectiveness in safeguarding data during training in edge environments.
- (vii.) Zhang et al. (2021) introduce a lightweight data obfuscation technique for edge devices that transforms sensitive inputs into protected formats prior to cloud-based AI inference. Evaluated on tasks such as American Sign Language recognition and handwritten digit classification, their method preserved model accuracy within 2–3% of the original while substantially reducing the risk of input reconstruction attacks. This privacy-aware pre-processing approach strikes a practical balance between security and usability, making it a viable solution for edge applications that still rely on cloud resources for computation.
- (viii.) Khan et al. (2024) present a privacy-preserving AI framework for edge devices leveraging the CKKS(Cheon–Kim–Kim–Song) homomorphic encryption scheme. The study addresses the long-standing trade-off between data confidentiality

and computational efficiency in constrained environments such as IoT sensors and mobile devices. By optimizing the encryption pipeline to minimize noise growth during computation, the framework maintains high model accuracy while enabling secure inference directly on encrypted data. The results demonstrate that homomorphic encryption, traditionally seen as computationally intensive, can be rendered practical for edge intelligence when carefully engineered. This work advances the feasibility of deploying encrypted AI workloads at the edge without compromising performance or privacy.

- (ix.) Liao, Li & Nadkarni (2025) present a comprehensive survey on secure machine learning, focusing on how secure multi-party computation (SMPC) is increasingly integrated into machine learning workflows. The paper reviews key contributions that support collaborative model training while preserving privacy, highlights optimizations in frameworks and domain-specific languages, and assesses applicability across both semi-honest and malicious threat models. It underscores MPC's growing practicality in privacy-sensitive environments

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts an experimental comparative analysis framework to assess the trade-offs between cloud-based inference and on-device inference for privacy-sensitive AI applications. An identical AI model was implemented in two configurations: (a) cloud-based inference and (b) on-device inference. Both configurations utilized the same dataset and model architecture. Key performance indicators, such as privacy exposure, latency, accuracy, and energy

consumption, were systematically measured and compared.

Model and Dataset

The experimental task was Human Activity Recognition (HAR) using the publicly available UCI HAR dataset, a benchmark comprising time-series data from smartphone accelerometers and gyroscopes. The model selected was a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) optimized for mobile inference. Deployment configurations were as follows: (i) On-device inference, implemented using TensorFlow Lite, (ii) Cloud-based inference, implemented using TensorFlow/Keras and deployed on a cloud environment.

Experimental Implementation

To examine performance differences, the HAR system was deployed in two configurations: (i) On-Device Learning, whereby the CNN was trained and deployed using TensorFlow Lite on two platforms: (a) Raspberry Pi 4 (4 GB RAM), and (b) Samsung Android smartphone (4 GB RAM, Octa-core CPU); (ii) Cloud Processing, wherein the same CNN model was hosted on Google Cloud AI Platform, with sensor data transmitted from the mobile device to the cloud via a RESTful API for inference.

Testing Protocol: Each configuration was tested using 100 real-time activity samples from multiple users performing five distinct activities: *walking, standing, sitting, lying down, and walking upstairs*. The evaluation metrics included four key measures. **Privacy exposure** was assessed by analysing the type and volume of data transmitted off-device. **Accuracy** was quantified using precision, recall, and F1-score. **Latency** was measured as the elapsed time from data input to the generation of an inference result. Energy consumption was monitored using Android Profiler for the smartphone and

external power sensors for the Raspberry Pi.

Model Architecture

The convolutional neural network (CNN) employed in this study was designed for lightweight, mobile-friendly inference. The model accepted input sequences consisting of 128-time steps of accelerometer and gyroscope data across six channels. Its architecture comprised

two convolutional layers, a single max-pooling layer, one dense layer, and a softmax output layer. The total model size was approximately 1.2 MB, optimized for deployment on resource-constrained devices. Training was performed using the original dataset, after which the model was quantized to further reduce storage requirements and inference latency for deployment on both the Raspberry Pi and the Android device.

Side-by-side diagram showing data flow for:

- A. Cloud-based processing: Data → Cloud Model → Result
- B. On-device processing: Data → Local Model → Result

Fig 1. Schematic diagram of CNN model architecture

3.5 Privacy Assessment: Simulated attacks such as membership inference and data reconstruction were performed on both models to assess their privacy resilience. Also, assessment of the ease of compliance with GDPR/NDPR principles such as data minimization and user consent were made.

3.5.1 Privacy Risk Evaluation

(i.) **Cloud Inference:** Full raw sensor data was transmitted, there was a potential exposure to man-in-the-middle attacks and centralized data breaches. The experimentation shows vulnerability to *membership inference* and *model inversion attacks*, where cloud models were insufficiently protected.

(ii.) **On-Device Inference:** No data was transmission. The model and the entire

data remain on the device. There was a strong resistance to remote data leakage. Although local attack vectors (physical access) remain but can be

mitigated via encryption and secure enclaves.

4.0 Results and Analysis

4.1 Performance Evaluation

Table 1: Evaluation Criteria

Metric	Cloud Processing	On-Device Learning
Data Privacy	High exposure	Minimal exposure
Accuracy	High (baseline)	Moderate–High
Latency	Network-dependent	Low
Energy Usage	Low (offloaded)	High (local compute)

Table 2: Performance Result of Accuracy

Deployment Mode	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Cloud Inference	94.7%	94.9%	94.5%	94.7%
On-Device Inference (Pi)	92.8%	93.1%	92.4%	92.7%
On-Device Inference (Smartphone)	93.3%	93.5%	93.1%	93.3%

Table 2 shows that on-device inference achieved comparable accuracy to the cloud model, with less than a 2% drop. The smartphone performed slightly better than the Raspberry Pi due to higher compute power.

Table 3: Performance Result of Latency (Average Per Inference)

Deployment Mode	Latency (ms)
Cloud (incl. transmission)	450 ms
On-Device (Pi)	170 ms
On-Device (Smartphone)	90 ms

Table 3 shows that On-device inference significantly reduced latency, especially in environments with limited or unstable internet connectivity.

Table 4: Performance Result of Energy Consumption (per 100 inferences)

Device/Mode	Energy Used (mAh)
Cloud (mobile upload + inference)	75 mAh
On-Device (Pi)	320 mAh
On-Device (Smartphone)	180 mAh

Table 4 shows that Cloud inference is more energy efficient because local computation is minimized. However, energy cost increases during network

congestion or mobile data use. On-device processing demands more power but offers predictable energy profiles without connectivity reliance.

Fig 2: Comparative Performance by Deployment Mode **Figure 3: Privacy Risk Surface**
Fig 3 :as a bar-based privacy risk surface, showing the likelihood of data leakage for cloud inference, federated learning, and on-device learning.

Table 5. Summary of Comparative Findings

Metric	Cloud-Based Processing	On-Device Learning (Edge AI)
Privacy Exposure	High	Low
Inference Accuracy	High	Slightly Lower
Latency	Network-dependent	Very Low
Energy Efficiency	High (if network stable)	Lower
Scalability	Easy	Device-dependent
GDPR/NDPR Compliance	Requires strict safeguards	More compliant by design

4.2 Overall Comparative Trade-Offs

The comparative analysis between cloud processing and on-device learning reveals clear trade-offs across data privacy, accuracy, latency, and energy efficiency.

In terms of data privacy, cloud-based inference exposes sensitive user data during transmission, thereby posing a significant risk when handling health records, financial information, or personal communications. By contrast, on-device learning eliminates the need to transfer raw data externally, since computation is executed locally. This gives on-device approaches a notable privacy advantage, particularly in regulatory environments or application domains where data confidentiality is non-negotiable, as shown in Table 1.

Looking at accuracy, as indicated from Table 2, cloud inference demonstrates the strongest performance, achieving 94.7%

accuracy, with a precision of 94.9%, recall of 94.5%, and an F1 score of 94.7%. On-device learning, however, shows only a marginal reduction in predictive quality. Experiments on smartphones reached 93.3% accuracy (F1: 93.3%), while Raspberry Pi deployments achieved 92.8% accuracy (F1: 92.7%). This indicates that on-device methods incur no more than a two-percentage point loss in accuracy compared to cloud inference. The trade-off, therefore, is minimal when considered against the privacy and latency benefits of edge execution.

When assessing latency as shown in Table 4, the differences are more pronounced. Cloud inference averaged 450 milliseconds per inference, largely due to transmission overheads and round-trip delays to remote servers. By contrast, local execution on Raspberry Pi reduced inference time to 170 milliseconds, and

smartphones delivered the fastest response at 90 milliseconds per inference. This means that on-device learning can achieve a three-to-five-fold latency improvement over the cloud. In real-time applications such as autonomous driving or medical monitoring, where milliseconds can be decisive, this advantage significantly outweighs the minor loss in accuracy.

The story changes when considering energy efficiency, as indicated in Table 5. Cloud inference consumed 75 mAh per 100 inferences, making it the most energy-efficient option because intensive computation is shifted away from the device. On-device inference required greater power expenditure, with smartphones consuming 180 mAh and Raspberry Pi consuming 320 mAh for the same number of tasks. This indicates that while on-device approaches reduce dependence on network availability, they impose a higher and more predictable energy cost, which may affect battery-constrained devices during prolonged operations.

Taken together, these comparisons highlight deployment suitability. Cloud inference is better suited for scenarios where high accuracy and energy efficiency are paramount, and where stable network connectivity can be guaranteed. On-device learning, on the other hand, is more appropriate for applications that demand low latency and strict privacy protections, even at the expense of higher energy consumption. Among edge options, smartphones strike the best balance, combining strong accuracy at 93.3% with low latency of 90 milliseconds and moderate energy consumption of 180 mAh. The Raspberry Pi, though slightly less efficient in both accuracy and energy, remains a cost-effective alternative in constrained edge environments where affordability and local processing are more important than absolute performance.

Ultimately, the evidence underscores a key insight: while cloud inference continues to

lead in accuracy and energy conservation, it lags significantly in latency and privacy. On-device learning, in contrast, ensures faster responsiveness and better data protection, making it highly attractive in sensitive and real-time applications. The choice between the two approaches therefore depends less on raw accuracy and more on the broader performance context of the intended application.

5.0 Discussion

The results show that on-device learning offers compelling advantages in privacy preservation and latency, making it a suitable approach for real-time applications in healthcare, finance, and personal devices. However, cloud processing remains advantageous for more complex models or resource-constrained devices due to its energy efficiency and scalability.

The marginal drop in accuracy on edge devices suggests that model quantization and compression techniques are effective in preserving performance while reducing computational demands. Furthermore, the trade-off in energy consumption is offset by the significant reduction in privacy risk, particularly for applications where user data sensitivity is high. This supports the growing interest in privacy-preserving edge AI, especially as regulatory bodies increasingly demand data minimization, local processing, and user consent.

The comparative results presented in this study reinforce the emerging view that on-device AI processing offers significant privacy advantages over traditional cloud-based architectures. By eliminating the need to transmit sensitive data across networks, on-device learning naturally aligns with privacy-by-design principles and regulatory requirements such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR). This local-first approach is especially critical in domains where data sensitivity is paramount, such

as healthcare diagnostics, personal finance, and biometric authentication.

5.1 Privacy-Performance Trade-offs:

The experimental findings confirm that on-device learning reduces privacy exposure significantly. This is a result attributed to the containment of both data and inference processes within the device. However, this privacy benefit comes with measurable trade-offs. While the accuracy of on-device models was only marginally lower than cloud-based models (within 2%), the energy consumption was noticeably higher. This is particularly important for battery-powered devices such as smartphones or wearable sensors, where power management is a critical design consideration. Latency also emerged as a key differentiator. On-device processing consistently delivered faster inference times, unaffected by network delays or server response times. This positions edge AI as a suitable solution for real-time applications such as fall detection, emergency response, or anomaly detection in critical systems.

5.2 Practical Considerations and Deployment Contexts:

From a deployment standpoint, hardware capability remains the primary limitation of on-device learning. Edge devices with limited processing power may struggle to support more complex AI models or multi-task learning scenarios. In contrast, cloud platforms can scale efficiently and support high-complexity models without impacting local device resources. Thus, a hybrid architecture may be preferable in certain contexts, where preliminary filtering or classification is performed locally, and deeper analysis is offloaded to the cloud. Another practical concern is model update and retraining. While on-device inference preserves privacy, updating models securely and efficiently across thousands of devices presents logistical and security challenges. Techniques such as federated learning, secure model update pipelines,

and over-the-air (OTA) encrypted deployments could help bridge this gap.

5.3 Security and Attack Surface:

Although on-device learning improves data privacy, it does not fully eliminate security risks. Local storage and model weights can be compromised through side-channel attacks or device theft. Therefore, security-enhanced hardware such as Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and secure enclaves (e.g., ARM TrustZone, Apple Secure Enclave) should be leveraged to ensure tamper-resistant execution. Additionally, incorporating differential privacy and encrypted model inference could provide further protection, especially in high-stakes applications.

6.0 Conclusion

This study offers a rigorous comparative assessment of on-device learning and cloud-based AI processing, analyzed through the dimensions of privacy, accuracy, latency, and energy consumption. The results demonstrate that on-device learning constitutes a feasible and privacy-preserving alternative to centralized AI systems, particularly in applications requiring real-time inference on sensitive data. Although a modest reduction in accuracy (less than 2%) and higher energy demands were observed, these trade-offs are often offset by improvements in latency and data protection. Cloud-based AI, by contrast, remains the most suitable option for large-scale, computationally intensive tasks, though its dependence on continuous data transmission presents enduring privacy risks.

Taken together, the findings highlight the importance of adopting a privacy-first design philosophy in the development of edge AI. Future research should extend this comparative analysis by investigating hybrid architectures that integrate cloud and edge capabilities, exploring advanced model compression and optimization

techniques, and conducting domain-specific deployment studies at scale. Such work will be essential to refine the balance between performance efficiency, energy sustainability, and privacy protection in next-generation AI systems.

7.0 Recommendations

Future AI deployment strategies should adopt a holistic framework that explicitly balances computational performance with privacy preservation. This requires the integration of decision-support models that systematically compare edge and cloud paradigms, enabling stakeholders to make informed choices based on context, efficiency, and privacy sensitivity.

To ensure rigor and comparability, the establishment of a standardized benchmarking framework is essential for evaluating privacy-preserving techniques, particularly in resource-constrained environments such as mobile and IoT devices. AI developers are further advised to follow evidence-based deployment guidelines that align system design with the sensitivity of processed data and the operational requirements of diverse application domains, thereby promoting responsible and context-aware AI adoption.

In addition, privacy safeguards should extend beyond algorithms to include system-level architectural strategies, such as computational partitioning, localized data processing, and secure communication protocols that enhance protection without compromising system efficiency. Collectively, these measures will contribute to the advancement of privacy-first AI systems that remain scalable, efficient, and ethically aligned across application domains.

8.0 References

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